

Design of growth-coupled measurements of orthogonal aminoacyl-tRNA synthetase function

A proposal for onboarding orthogonal aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases to the protein sequence-to-function measurement platform.

- Uses a gene circuit to tie successful suppression of UAG stop codons by non-canonical amino acids to bacterial cell growth
- Calibration variants span the dynamic range of activity enable quantitative function measurements
- First dataset collection will focus on measuring variants of the *Methanocaldococcus jannaschii* tyrosyl-tRNA synthetase

This document was created as a part of the Pooled, Growth-Based Assays for Protein Function Measurements pipeline¹ for Align to Innovate's Open Dataset Initiative. Align to Innovate is a non-profit research organization operating under open science principles with the goal of improving science research with programmable experiments. The Open Datasets Initiative is working to accelerate community-driven science with the use of automated labs to pioneer robust data collection methods and curated, high-fidelity, public biological datasets amenable to machine learning. This work was supported by Align to Innovate's Open Datasets Initiative which receives philanthropic funding in part from Griffin Catalyst

Contributors

Align to Innovate:

Peter Kelly - Program Director, Open Datasets Initiative

Dana Cortade, Ph.D. - Technical Project Manager, Open Datasets Initiative

Proposal Co-Leaders:

Ross Thyer, Ph.D. - Asst. Prof., Dept. of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, Rice University.

David Ross, Ph.D. - Living Measurement Systems Foundry, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)

Reviewers:

Andre Pulschen, Ph.D., Biodesign Lab, The Francis Crick Institute

Akos Nyerges, Ph.D., Research Associate in Genetics at Harvard Medical School, Boston, US

Devon Stork, Ph.D., Pioneer Labs

Osaid Ather, MB BChir, Biodesign Lab, The Francis Crick Institute

Raghav Shroff, Ph.D., Assistant Research Professor, Houston Methodist Research Institute

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Context, Significance, and Impact

Across all domains of life, the proteome is synthesized from twenty standard amino acid monomers and a further two, rarely occurring non-canonical amino acids, which use specialized translational machinery to reassign specific stop signals in the mRNA. Advances in our understanding of the translational machinery, both at the structural and mechanistic level, have enabled researchers to similarly co-opt the stop signals in mRNA to enable the introduction of a large range of non-canonical or entirely unnatural amino acids into proteins (collectively ncAAs). These new protein chemistries can bring significant functionality to proteins beyond those found in the standard amino acids, including a variety of bio-orthogonal conjugation chemistries, photoactivatable chemistries, and novel architecture for coordination of metals. In general, incorporation of these new chemistries requires initially identifying a suitable orthogonal translation system (OTS) to serve as the scaffold and a subsequent protein engineering campaign to enable it to accommodate the new substrate.

For the most common orthogonal aminoacyl-tRNA synthetases (aaRSs), the tyrosyl-tRNA synthetase from *Methanocaldococcus jannaschii* (MjY) and the pyrrolysyl-tRNA synthetase from *Methanosarcina* species, researchers have developed a good understanding of the relative contributions of the amino

acids which line the substrate binding pockets, and it is now possible to rapidly engineer variants capable of incorporating a given ncAA into proteins (Fig. 1a). However, the degree of discrimination these variants achieve between their native substrate and the new non-canonical substrate (or between multiple non-canonical substrates) is highly variable, and the underlying ruleset governing these interactions is not well understood. Ultimately, most aaRS engineered for non-canonical substrates occupy a permissive state (Fig. 1a) where either the native substrate is also accepted and incorporation efficiency is largely driven by substrate concentration, or good discrimination against the parental amino acid is achieved, but several different ncAA are incorporated, even when lacking structural similarity. Engineering highly selective aaRS variants has proven extremely challenging but is vitally important as many of the intended applications of ncAAs are intolerant of heterogeneity in the protein sequence. For example, detailed kinetic characterization of new catalytic motifs containing ncAAs is near impossible when the enzyme represents a mixed population. Similarly, the development of protein therapeutics (biologics) containing ncAAs requires virtually perfect incorporation efficiency to satisfy regulatory requirements.

Figure 1: Schematic of orthogonal translation and dataset targets. (a) Representative pathway for ncAA incorporation using an orthogonal translation system. The Gen2 DOPA aaRS displays poor discrimination between L-tyrosine and L-DOPA. In contrast, the 3IY aaRS strongly discriminates against L-tyrosine. While it does not incorporate L-DOPA, it can accept other 3-substituted tyrosine analogs. (b) Proposed aaRS variants and ncAAs to be evaluated to improve discrimination against tyrosine. (c) Proposed aaRS variants and ncAAs to be evaluated to investigate accommodation of bulky naphthyl groups in different orientations. The NapA aaRS is extremely permissive, but its ability to accommodate naphthyl groups connected at the 1- position is unknown. The CouA aaRS contains additional mutations at two loci which may be needed to accommodate the group in a different orientation.

Mapping cryptic loci which control substrate discrimination in the MjY aaRS.

In collaboration with researchers at NIST, who are separately participating in the Align to Innovate Open Datasets Initiative, we have developed a modular version of their TetA-based, high throughput fitness landscape measurement platform² which additionally incorporates a fused fluorescent reporter protein (Fig. 2a-b)³. We propose to further adapt the TetA-mScarlet reporter by introducing between one and three UAG codons in place of poorly conserved residues within the cytoplasmic loops. This modification will enable it to confer tetracycline resistance in response to UAG codon suppression by natural or non-canonical amino acids. In this scheme, aaRS library variants are matched with unique DNA barcodes located elsewhere on the expression plasmid using long-read DNA sequencing. A population of *E. coli* cells containing both the TetA-mScarlet reporter and aaRS library variants is exposed to a gradient of tetracycline and ncAA concentrations and fitness of all variants in the population is measured by the change in abundance of the DNA barcodes to explore the interplay between these two variables. Adaptation of this system, which both the Thyer research group and NIST have experience using for high-throughput fitness landscape measurements, will enable large, high-quality datasets to be collected within the time frame of this project.

To map the important loci, both expected and cryptic, in an orthogonal aaRS, we propose constructing a deep mutational scanning (DMS) library of the MjY aaRS. The MjY aaRS is proposed for two reasons: (i) it is well characterized and thus provides a large amount of mutagenesis data which can serve as internal controls to determine the quality of the dataset, and (ii), competition with the canonical amino acid tyrosine and resulting incorporation into proteins is a significant problem that needs to be overcome, unlike pyrrolysyl-tRNA synthetases which do not encounter their native substrate (pyrrolysine) in recombinant hosts. Importantly, our own previous work with this enzyme has identified a cryptic residue (Y119F) which influences substrate specificity but does not directly line the binding pocket

and would not be predicted based on our understanding of the protein's structure or sequence homology⁴.

For the DMS library construction, we propose a comprehensive library design which includes every single amino acid substitution spanning the entirety of the MjY aaRS coding sequence (306 residues) as well as every single deletion and insertion. This is a mature library construction technique within the Thyer research group, we have developed a python script for library construction which is freely available (github.com/Thyerlab/SPINE_Thyer) and to date have assembled eight such libraries of similar size and complexity. Importantly, inclusion of single amino acid insertions and deletions within the library adds significant value to the dataset as these mutations are normally inaccessible to traditional methods of library construction, such as mutagenic PCR.

We anticipate these datasets providing valuable information regarding three distinct facets of substrate discrimination: (i) residues which influence interactions between the p- and m-positions in tyrosine analogs, e.g. between L-tyrosine and L-DOPA, (ii) residues which function as global antideterminants for incorporation of the native substrate, L-tyrosine, L-DOPA, and 3-iodo-L-tyrosine, and (iii) accommodation of larger substrate analogs in different orientations, particularly those containing naphthyl derivatives. This information can be collected from a minimal series of high-quality datasets using the ncAAs listed in Figure 1b, which both span a range of different side chain sizes and properties, while each being objectively valuable engineering targets. Importantly, as the fitness landscape measurement platform derives fitness data of individual variants under multiple different conditions, such as a gradient of supplemented ncAA concentrations, a dedicated counter-selection to remove variants capable of incorporating the parental amino acid is not required. This critical information is captured by differential fitness scores between variants as the ncAA concentration increases. For example, variants with good discrimination against tyrosine are expected to have poor fitness (observed as low abundance of barcodes) only when the ncAA is absent, whereas the fitness of permissive variants is likely to be independent of ncAA concentration.

Figure 2: Schematic of the genetic reporter and dataset collection workflow. (a) Genetic circuit showing the aaRS and tRNA pair on one plasmid and the TetA-mScarlet-I translational fusion encoded by a second plasmid. Suppression of a UAG stop codon is required for the TetA component to confer resistance to tetracycline. (b) Between 1-3 UAG codons will be introduced at low conservation positions in the cytoplasmic loops of the TetA component. (c) Workflow of the fitness landscape measurement platform developed by NIST.

Completion of the proposed work is anticipated to yield the following outcomes.

1. Six comprehensive DMS datasets spanning two non-canonical amino acids (L-DOPA and 3-iodo-L-tyrosine) evaluated using three synthetase scaffolds intended to investigate discrimination between tyrosine and 3-substituted tyrosine analogs. The zero concentration of each ncAA effectively represents L-tyrosine, the wild-type substrate.
2. Six comprehensive DMS datasets spanning three non-canonical amino acids (3-(1-naphthyl)-L-alanine, 3-(2-naphthyl)-L-alanine, and L-(7-hydroxycoumarin-4-yl)-ethylglycine) evaluated using two synthetase scaffolds intended to investigate mutations required for substrate orientation. The zero concentration of each ncAA effectively represents L-tyrosine, the wild-type substrate.
3. A complete genotype-phenotype map which identifies the contribution of all residues in the widely used MjY aaRS to substrate specificity.
 - a. In a best-case scenario, this would yield valuable 'antideterminant' positions which can improve discrimination against the wild-type amino acid and may be compatible with the large number of existing MjY aaRS variants reported in the literature.
 - b. Cryptic loci which enhance incorporation of known ncAA substrates.
 - c. A list of candidate residues which can be used to generate small secondary libraries for fine-tuning substrate discrimination in conjunction with a counter-selection or additional round of fitness landscape measurement.
4. Physical library DNA and *E. coli* transformants containing the aaRS libraries which can be rescreened against additional nCAAs by us or other affiliated investigators.
5. A workflow and genetic reagents to enable rapid dataset collection on additional aaRS scaffolds, including the pyrrolyl-tRNA synthetase and the recently developed chimeric PheRS (ChPheRS)⁵.

Completion of the proposed work is anticipated to have the following impacts.

1. Open-source dataset collection efforts would complement other initiatives in the field aiming to centralize and compare aaRS engineering practices (e.g. iNclusive)⁶.
2. No similar datasets exist and the vast majority of the MjY sequence remains completely unexplored.
3. Datasets would be broadly useful in the chemical biology community and are anticipated to be of sufficient depth and quality to support the training of ML models to predict library designs and individual mutations to accommodate specific ncAA chemistries.

Gene of Interest (GOI) Region

The gene of interest will be placed in the second transcriptional unit on a destination plasmid with two different configurations to be evaluated (Fig. 3 and 4). The first design uses a large segment of legacy DNA and is intended to reduce complications arising from modularizing the tRNA which can be highly toxic in certain contexts.

Figure 3: Two proposed designs for the single plasmid system which contains both the dual screening-selection cassette and the GOI. Red bars within the reporter in TU1 represent UAG codons. (a) In the first design, the second transcriptional unit is occupied by a region of legacy DNA derived from pEvol-family plasmids which places the aaRS (GOI) under the control of the PBAD promoter. (b) In the second design, both the aaRS and its tRNA are fully modularized and placed under the control of inducible promoters to prevent leaky expression contributing to incorporation of L-tyrosine.

Figure 4: GOI region of the two proposed designs. Designs (a) and (b) represent the legacy and modular GOI regions respectively.

Selection Cassette

The selection cassette is a region of the plasmid that is specific to each function (Fig. 5). The selection cassette contains the function-specific circuit components with which the GOI will interact (UAG codons which will be suppressed) and all of the necessary reporters produced by the interaction (e.g., antibiotic resistance gene, TetA) for fitness measurements and a fluorescent protein of choice used for function measurements during development (i.e., singleplex function measurements). Successful suppression of UAG stop codons with either the canonical amino acid L-tyrosine or the non-canonical amino acid L-DOPA will result in the production

of TetA and confer tetracycline resistance. However, these different incorporation events can be measured by the output of Or-GFP, which has different spectral properties depending on the identity of the residue forming the chromophore. DOPA incorporation at this position results in a dramatic red shift and will be used as a secondary validation in the initial testing using FACS. For the other aaRS genes, a different GFP variant will be used which contains a UAG stop codon at a permissive location (residue 151). A translationally fused design was selected for this project to ensure the tightest possible coupling between the TetA fitness readout and the fluorescent reporter signal.

Proposed Hosts and Plasmid Design

The host cells will either be *E. coli* DH10B or *E. coli* B95. ΔA . Strain choice will be based upon performance of the TetA reporter containing one or two UAG stop codons. If initial testing in *E. coli* DH10B, which is termination competent at UAG stop codons, does not demonstrate sufficient stop

codon suppression as measured by tetracycline resistance and fluorescence from the tethered reporter, then *E. coli* B95. ΔA will be used. Our initial benchling plasmid design file can be viewed at the following link: <https://benchling.com/s/seq-1LqU1klhQ6po9pjY8tlp/edit>

Proposed Controls for Assay Development

Stage 1 - Development and Tuning

For the orthogonal aaRS dataset, in Stage 1, the tuning sequences will be those listed in Table 1 to access a range of function that spans the desired assay range. In addition to the gradient of L-DOPA concentrations, a dedicated control with 1 mM supplemented L-tyrosine will be included if space permits. Identical media compositions and ncAA batch numbers will be used by the Thyer research group and NIST to minimize external variation between assays.

Substrate/s	GOI sequences	Expected activity
Tyrosine/DOPA	MjY aaRS WT	Strong tyrosine incorporation, limited/no DOPA incorporation
Tyrosine/DOPA	MjY aaRS DOPA Gen 2	Mixed DOPA and tyrosine incorporation

Table 1: The substrate and aaRS combinations that will be used.

Stage 2 - Normalization and Calibration Controls

In Stage 2, the candidate normalization and calibration controls will be determined, as listed in Table 2. The proposed controls should be sufficient to produce an “always-on” phenotype, which is needed for normalization sequences and enough calibration sequences to span the desired dynamic range.

Substrate (ncAA)	aaRS (GOI)	Expected activity	Type of Control
DOPA	MjY aaRS wt	UAG suppression at all DOPA concentrations – green fluorescence	Normalization
DOPA	MjY aaRS DOPA Gen 2	UAG suppression at all DOPA concentrations – green to orange fluorescence gradient	Normalization
DOPA	MjY aaRS DOPA Gen 2 2xTAA	Inactive	Calibration
3IY	MjY aaRS 3IY	UAG suppression and green fluorescence correlated with [3IY]	Calibration
NapA	MjY aaRS NapA	UAG suppression and green fluorescence correlated with [NapA]	Calibration
CouA	MjY aaRS CouA	UAG suppression and green fluorescence correlated with [CouA]	Calibration

Table 2: aaRS and substrate pairs for developing normalization and calibration controls.

Secondary Validation and Data Analysis

Initial validations performed using the Gen2 DOPA aaRS can take advantage of the tethered orange-GFP reporter to match DNA barcodes enriched using the tetracycline selection to those which are enriched using FACS. These validation experiments can be performed at NIST if needed. Synthetase variants which are determined to have beneficial properties will be characterized by fluorescence assays using a permissive GFP variant in the presence (100 uM and 1 mM) of relevant ncAAs along with a media control. New aaRS variants capable of incorporating L-DOPA will be evaluated using the

Orange-GFP reporter. Secondary validation of variants with desirable properties, particularly those which display better discrimination against L-tyrosine, will be performed using mass spectrometry. Additional quality assurance steps which may be taken using the collected data include using LANTERN (landscape interpretable nonparametric model) to predict the genotype-phenotype relationship of mutants when trained on subsets of the data (LANTERN: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2114021119>).

Pilot-Scale Collection Targets

We will construct deep mutational scanning (DMS) libraries in two phases, starting with the wild type tyrosyl-tRNA synthetase from *Methanocaldococcus jannaschii* (MjY), the Gen2 DOPA aaRS variant, and the 3IY aaRS variant. For the DMS library construction, we propose a comprehensive library design which includes every single amino acid substitution spanning the entirety of the coding sequences (306 residues) as well as every single deletion and insertion. These libraries will be measured against two ncAAs: L-DOPA, 3-iodo-L-tyrosine, both 3-substituted tyrosine analogs, but incorporated by synthetases with vastly different abilities to

exclude the parental amino acid tyrosine. The zero concentration of each ncAA effectively represents L-tyrosine, the wild-type substrate, which is present in LB at 1-1.4 mM. Once the workflow for measurements with the initial aaRS libraries has been established, additional scanning mutagenesis libraries will be constructed on the engineered synthetases for 3-(2-naphthyl)-L-alanine and L-(7-hydroxycoumarin-4-yl)-ethylglycine. These will be evaluated specifically to search for residues which are important for substrate orientation. It is anticipated that data will be incidentally collected which provides additional information on residues important for discrimination against L-tyrosine.

Large-Scale Collection Targets

Larger datasets may be collected by sampling a larger mutational space within synthetase scaffolds, either through additional random mutagenesis on top of the deep mutational scanning library or multi-position site saturation mutagenesis, expanding the set of amino acid chemistries evaluated for a given aaRS, or investigating additional synthetases, each with its own unique pool of ncAA chemistries (Figure 6). Proposed goals for larger scale data collection include: (i) evaluation of different pyrrolysyl-tRNA synthetases which are commonly engineered

for genetic code expansion including the *Methanosarcina mazei* PyIRS (MmPyIRS), *M. barkeri* PyIRS (MbPyIRS), and the *M. acetivorans* PyIRS (MaPyIRS), (ii) scanning mutagenesis of recently developed chimeric aaRS variants which encode proof-reading domains capable of removing the parental amino acid, but traditionally suffer from poor activity, and (iii) measuring the impact of mutations within a given aaRS on the incorporation of a curated set of ncAAs and developing models to predict the ability to incorporate new ncAA chemistries.

References

1. Cortade, D., d'Oelsnitz, S., Chadha, A., Hayes, O., Taghon, G., Doerr, M., Born, S., Kelly, P., Ross, D., DeBenedictis, E., & Align to Innovate. Design of a generalized platform for gathering protein sequence → function datasets at scale. (2024) doi:10.5281/zenodo.12521641.
2. Tack, D. S. *et al.* The genotype-phenotype landscape of an allosteric protein. *Mol. Syst. Biol.* **17**, e10179 (2021).
3. Bindels, D. S. *et al.* mScarlet: a bright monomeric red fluorescent protein for cellular imaging. *Nat. Methods* **14**, 53–56 (2017).
4. Thyer, R. *et al.* Directed Evolution of an Improved Aminoacyl-tRNA Synthetase for Incorporation of L-3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine (L-DOPA). *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed Engl.* **60**, 14811–14816 (2021).
5. Ding, W. *et al.* Chimeric design of pyrrolysyl-tRNA synthetase/tRNA pairs and canonical synthetase/tRNA pairs for genetic code expansion. *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 3154 (2020).
6. Icking, L.-S. *et al.* iNclusive: a database collecting useful information on non-canonical amino acids and their incorporation into proteins for easier genetic code expansion implementation. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **52**, D476–D482 (2024).